

STUDENTS' ASSESSMENT OF THE ADOPTION OF GOOGLE TOOLS FOR LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING USING THE UTAUT MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The College of Teacher Education has jumped the wagon of delivering course contents through flexible means. As such, teachers and students have immersed themselves in the use of applications paid for by the University. Undeniably, due to the onslaught of the pandemic and the continued policy on remote education, the Google Workspace For Education (GWFE) Applications have become integral to the teaching and learning process. This study involved the adoption of GWFE. It aimed to explore the students' assessment of this adoption in view of the teaching and learning of language. Eighty BSED major in English students participated in this study by filling out an online questionnaire composed of three parts frequency of the use of Google tools, assessment of the adoption of GWFE, and the challenges in using these adapted tools. The first two sections of the questionnaire were completed using a 4-point scale. Findings revealed that students observed that their teachers usually used productive and communication tools such as Classroom, which was used as a site to deliver content, and Meet, which was used during synchronous classes. Overall, students have a positive view on the adoption although they noted some challenges experienced by their teachers i.e. proficiency in the full use of the features of the Google applications and sticking only to slides presentation in delivering content. Moreover, relative to the products made available through the domain purchase of the University, not many were used. Therefore, further research on the utilization of the Google tools using another model and using teachers, as well as students from other majors, as respondents are suggested. Nevertheless, the findings may be used as bases in crafting course packs for the flexible learning class.

Keywords: Google Workspace for Education, Google tools, language teaching and learning, educational technology, descriptive research